

Theoretical Importance Of Anthropocentric Phraseological Units

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Abstract: *In this article the importance of anthropocentric phraseology is revealed with clear examples. An interpretation of the differentiation of understanding “scientific” and “naïve” definitions of discussed phraseological units with examples is presented. The importance and relevance of phraseological units in the system of linguistic, national and cultural coloring in interlingual analysis are revealed, orientation to the realities of the universe surrounding the individual is presented.*

Keywords — anthropocentric character, phraseology, linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, idioms, linguocognitive, phraseologisms, national mentality.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the essence of language provides an opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of the spiritual heritage, rich history, national values, cultural and spiritual values of any nation. The relationship between language and culture, the understanding of national mentality reveals the very essence of language, its communicative function. In such areas of world linguistics as linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, ethnolinguistics, discursive analysis, the personality factor is in the center of research analysis.

The development and study of phraseology as a science has been conducted for a long time. Phraseology is a branch of lexicology studying phraseological units (set expressions, phraseologisms, or idioms (in foreign linguistics). Phraseological units differ from free word-groups semantically and structurally. Phraseological units, also known as idiomatic expressions, are fixed combinations of words that function as a single unit with a specific meaning. These expressions often have a figurative or non-literal meaning that cannot be deduced from the individual meanings of the words within the unit. Phraseological units are an important aspect of language and play a significant role in communication, adding richness, expressiveness, and cultural nuances to speech and writing.

Phraseological units can vary in length, from short idioms to longer expressions or proverbs. They can be present in various forms, including verb phrases, noun phrases, or prepositional phrases. They are deeply embedded in the language, are widely used by native speakers; they reflect cultural and contextual aspects of a language, and their understanding often requires familiarity with the language and its associated traditions, history, and idiomatic usage.

When learning a language, it is important to know its grammatical and lexical composition but to “understand” a

given language it is important to refer to its phraseological composition. Phraseological units convey the characteristics of a particular language, as well as features of the worldview of people who speak it: they carry in their content the experience accumulated by the people, convey a description of the linguistic picture of the world of a given nationality. Most phraseological units not only name the phenomena of reality but also characterize these phenomena in a certain way.

Anthropocentric, communicative, linguocognitive approach to language, the relationship of language and culture, the understanding of national mentality, the need for an in-depth scientific study of the essence of language, its communicative function are the main objective of this article.

Anthropocentrism was formed as a direction that aimed to approach language and its phenomena from the perspective of the human factor. The emergence of anthropocentric orientation is associated with a deeper study of man in science, the process of describing linguistic activity in conjunction with the personality factor. Anthropocentric study of language means to show the mentality of a particular people, its national identity. For this reason, it is advisable to say that phraseology is anthropocentric in nature, manifested in the presence of phraseological units with components or a figurative component that convey realities associated either with the person himself/herself (parts of the human body, character traits) or with the reality surrounding him/her. It can be argued that the anthropocentrism of phraseology is universal for all language systems, and not a national-specific feature of the language of a single ethnic group.

The notion “anthropocentrism” is being actual in linguistic nowadays for many reason. If we take a look linguocultural differences of phraseological units in English and Uzbek language this approach helps to understand how human-centered expressions reflect cultural values, beliefs, and perspectives in these two languages. Firstly, it helps to make comparative analysis of English and Uzbek: a) Comparing

anthropocentric phraseological units in English and Uzbek reveals unique cultural values, societal norms, and historical influences embedded in language.

b) Differences in expressions related to human behavior highlight distinct cultural perspectives on relationships, ethics, emotions, and social roles. For example: It reveals cultural perspectives of the two languages. English phraseological units often reflect Western cultural values, emphasizing individualism, pragmatism, and direct communication while Uzbek phraseological units may showcase values such as collectivism, respect for traditions, and indirect communication styles influenced by Central Asian cultural norms. In addition, anthropocentric approach helps to learn human relationship in two nations. As expression in English may focus on individual characteristics, emotions, and interpersonal relationships with a pragmatic or humorous tone, Uzbek expressions could highlight communal ties, familial bonds, and societal hierarchies, reflecting a more collective approach to human relationships. Another important aspect of this approach is that it helps us to learn historical and religious influences. English expressions may reflect historical events, literary works, or religious references that shape the cultural understanding of human experiences while Uzbek phraseological units were influenced by Islamic traditions, folklore, or historical narratives that underpin societal values and ethical principles. This approach is also very useful when it comes to linguistic features of two languages. For example, English phraseological units may feature idiomatic expressions, proverbs, or colloquialisms that reflect the dynamic nature of the language. Uzbek expressions might include poetic imagery, traditional sayings, or metaphors rooted in the rich linguistic heritage of the region. Lastly, anthropocentric approach is the indicator of modern influences. Contemporary English expressions may incorporate pop culture references, technological terms, or global trends that resonate with diverse audiences. Modern Uzbek phraseological units could integrate borrowed words, international concepts, or adaptations from other languages in response to globalization and cultural exchange. Researchers employing the anthropocentric paradigm may conduct qualitative analyses of phraseological units, examining their semantic, syntactic, and pragmatic dimensions. Fieldwork, interviews with native speakers, and corpus-based studies can help uncover the cultural nuances embedded in anthropocentric expressions.

By conducting a detailed comparative analysis of anthropocentric phraseological units in English and Uzbek, researchers can uncover deeper insights into how language mirrors cultural values, societal norms, and historical legacies in these distinct linguistic contexts. This exploration can enrich cross-cultural understanding, language education, and intercultural communication practices between speakers of English and Uzbek.

Thanks to the anthropocentric model of perception of the surrounding universe, the scope of the concept expands, in which everyday classification, taking into account the correlation of a holistic visual image, endows this concept with

additional characteristics and qualities that were not previously inherent in it and differentiate it from scientific classification. The formation of such a model is largely due to the existence in the phraseology of numerous units that have somatisms in their composition, i.e. words that objectify the sphere of corporeality and point to different parts of the human body. These include, for example, Russian phraseological units “to the roots of the hair” (blush to the roots of the hair) - “with your whole being, entirely, completely”, “under your breath” (speak under your breath) - “speak very quietly, indistinctly, “in the eyes” (*Nega mavzuda o'zbek va ingliz tili turib rus tilidan misol beryapsiz?*). With the help of such phraseological units, a certain pattern can be identified: the characteristic external signs of parts of the human body (hair roots, nose, eyes, hands, etc.) are correlated by consciousness with different ideas about the standards of being (impact level, distance, volume level, direction, effort, threat factor, etc.), which increases the volume of these concepts, giving them a place in everyday classification. There are a number of phraseological units that facilitate the implementation of the concept of the universe, if we take into account the difference in the functions of objects that are quite close in scientific classification. For example, we can take for comparison the ideas about the characteristics of a person and human behavior, represented through the phraseological units “stand on your feet”, “kneel down” (submit, obey someone). In this particular situation, the knees are part of the legs, which is also opposed to them, because, being a component of phraseology, the somatism “knees” personifies an unworthy, shameful support, which differs from the semantics of somatism “legs”, which is a type of obligatory support laid down by nature.

The expansion of the scope of concepts that takes place in the “naïve” classification in relation to the scientific one is due to the figurativeness that most phraseological units possess. Let's take as an example the word “heart”, which in both English and Uzbek is interpreted as “the central organ of the circulatory system in the form of a muscle bag”, providing blood flow through the blood vessels. In the “naïve” classification, the heart is interpreted as a place of concentration of all feelings that arise in a person, which, in turn, is reflected in many phraseological units that use this component in their composition and represent such an idea of the universe as feelings (emotions): “with all my heart (quite sincerely); “take by the heart” (excite, make a strong impression); “a stone fell from the heart” (it became much easier after a difficult experience) and “yuraginga quloq tut” (you act or make a decision according to your feelings. This decision might not be the practical one, but it is the decision that really speaks to you.); “Yurakdan yurakka” (Share an intimate conversation. If someone wants to have a nice long chat with you, they might ask if you can have a “heart to heart”)., “qalxim sindi” (To give up, If you “lose heart”, you no longer believe that you can accomplish something or that something is for you. You have lost hope and are ready to give up).

The comparison of specific phraseological units is based on various aspects of the interlinguistic relationship of phraseological units in the theory of translation, in the theory

of phraseography, in comparative typological studies. The functional-semantic correlation of phraseological units in different languages shows the uniqueness of the semantic content, the combination of functional-semantic uniqueness and full phraseological equivalents in the general structure of the compared phraseological units.

Conclusion

The exploration of the anthropocentric paradigm in phraseological units reveals a profound interconnection between language, culture, and human cognition. By examining how human-centric perspectives shape the formation, interpretation, and usage of idiomatic expressions, we gain valuable insights into the intricate relationship between language and the human experience.

The anthropocentric paradigm not only underscores the centrality of human beings in shaping language but also highlights the cultural, cognitive, and social dimensions embedded in phraseological units. Through this lens, we recognize that idiomatic expressions are not merely linguistic artifacts but reflections of human thought patterns, emotions, beliefs, and interactions within specific cultural contexts.

Moreover, the study of the anthropocentric paradigm in phraseology offers a deeper understanding of how language both reflects and influences human perceptions of the world. By delving into the rich tapestry of idiomatic expressions rooted in anthropocentric concepts, we uncover layers of meaning, metaphorical associations, and cultural nuances that illuminate the complexities of human communication and expression.

Ultimately, the theoretical importance of the anthropocentric paradigm in phraseological units serves as a gateway to exploring the profound ways in which language embodies human experiences, values, and worldviews. By recognizing the pivotal role of human agency and cognition in shaping idiomatic expressions, we not only enhance our linguistic knowledge but also deepen our appreciation for the intricate interplay between language, culture, and the human condition.

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